

D5.4 - Implementation and validation of RESTORE

Use Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101036766.

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET	
Project Acronym	RESTORE
Project Full Title	Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC
Grant Agreement	101036766
Call Identifier	H2020-LC-GD-2020-1
Topic	Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system
Project Duration	48 months (October 2021 – September 2025)
Project Website	www.restore-dhc.eu
Disclaimer	The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the funding authorities. The funding authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION SHEET	
Number	Deliverable D5.4
Full Title	Report on Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors
Related WP	WP5
Related Task	Task T5.4: Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform Sub-Task T5.4.1: Use-Case I - Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors (Brønderslev, Denmark)
Lead Beneficiary	CENER
Author(s)	Rafael Pérez Santana (AALBORG CSP) - rps@aalborcsp.com
Contributor(s)	Miguel Herrador Moreno (AALBORG CSP) - mhm@aalborcsp.com Stefan Bergmann (SimTech) - s.bergmann@simtechnology.com
Reviewer(s)	Francisco Cabello Núñez (CENER) - fcabello@cener.com Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH) – f.dargam@simtechnology.com
Dissemination level	Public
Due Date	July 2025
Submission Date	July 31 st , 2025
Status	Final Version

QUALITY CONTROL ASSESSMENT SHEET			
ISSUE	DATE	COMMENT	AUTHOR
V0.1	21/07/2025	Draft Version 01	Rafael Pérez Santana (AALBORG CSP)
V0.2	23/07/2025	Draft Version 02 General Revision Contribution to Section 3, 4 and 6 Reviewed Version	Miguel Herrador Moreno (AALBORG CSP) Stefan Bergmann (SimTech) Francisco Cabello Núñez (CENER)
V1.0a	28/07/2025	Final Version	Rafael Pérez Santana (AALBORG CSP) Miguel Herrador Moreno (AALBORG CSP)
V1.0b	30/07/2025	Final Version Review	Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH) Francisco Cabello Núñez (CENER)
V1.0	31/07/2025	Final Version + Submission to the EC	Rafael Pérez Santana (AALBORG CSP) Miguel Herrador Moreno (AALBORG CSP) Francisco Cabello Núñez (CENER)

Summary

This deliverable presents the activities and outcomes of Task 5.4 within RESTORE EU project, which focuses on demonstrating the performance and replicability of the RESTORE integrated system in several facilities. The task consists of the implementation, optimization, and validation of six real use-cases through their digital representations, using the RESTORE Simulation Web Platform (IPSE GO). These virtual models aim to replicate real district heating and cooling (DHC) networks across diverse industrial and geographical contexts in Europe, including biomass and solar systems, cement and paper industries, steelworks, geothermal applications, and university campuses.

Deliverable D5.4 deals with the implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors.

The document details the methodological framework used to implement the Use-Case I (related to Sub-task T5.4.1), drawing on technical input from WP1 to WP4, and presenting simulation models for Use-Case I within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, resulting from the integration of the RESTORE concept in residential and industrial DH, using a scenario with biomass and solar collectors. For each use-case, the partners defined specific system boundaries, components, and operational conditions, which were then simulated and optimized in the platform. The work provides a technical validation of the RESTORE concept, and a structured dataset to support environmental impact assessment. The insights gathered here serve as a cornerstone for developing large-scale replication strategies in Task 5.5, facilitating broader deployment of RESTORE technologies across Europe.

Table of Contents

Summary	4
Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Baseline Plant: Brønderslev CHP Hybrid Plant	7
2.1. CHP Central Plant background	8
2.1.1. District Heating Network	9
2.2. Hybridized CCP & Biomass Plant.....	10
2.2.1. CCP Solar field	11
2.2.2. Biomass boilers and ORC	12
3. RESTORE TCES Integration.....	15
3.1. Use Case definition	15
3.2. IPSE GO Platform	19
3.3. Input Data.....	20
3.3.1. Initial Raw Input Data	20
3.3.2. Assumptions.....	21
3.3.3. Refined Data	23
Refined Variables Summary.....	23
3.3.4. End-user feedback	25
3.4. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation.....	27
3.4.1. UC1 Model definition	27
3.4.2. Charge Mode.....	28
3.4.3. Discharge Mode	30
4. Results.....	32
4.1. Process Simulations.....	32
4.1.1. Charge Mode.....	32
4.1.2. Discharge Mode	37
5. Conclusions	41
6. References	42

1. Introduction

Sub-task T5.4.1 (Use-Case I: The integration of the RESTORE concept in Residential and industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors) addresses the implementation and virtual replication of the RESTORE TCES concept within a Hybridized Combined Heat and Power that feed district heating network in the municipality of Brønderslev, in Denmark. This facility combines biomass boilers and solar thermal collectors (Parabolic Trough Collectors) to supply both residential and industrial heating demands. The objective is to integrate these technologies into the RESTORE simulation framework to assess their performance under different operational conditions and control strategies.

Led by AALBORG CSP, with the technical support of SIMTECH and contributions from CENER, the work in T5.4.1 involved defining the system mass and heat balances integration, available renewable energy sources and thermal chemical energy storage (TCES) configuration. The Use-Case I model was implemented within the IPSE GO platform, enabling interactive simulation, control testing, and optimization of system sizing and parameters involved.

This document is structured to present a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of the Use-Case I. It begins with a description of the baseline plant, including its technical background and configuration (Section 2). Section 3 focuses on the integration of the RESTORE TCES system, detailing the use-case definition, the role of the IPSE GO Platform, the input data (including assumptions and refinements), and the virtual implementation steps. Section 4 presents the simulation results, and the document concludes with key findings (Section 5) and references (Section 6).

2. Baseline Plant: Brønderslev CHP Hybrid Plant

The Brønderslev Combined Heat and Power (CHP) hybrid plant, located in Northern Jutland, Denmark, stands as a pioneering example of next-generation district energy systems. The plant represents a forward-thinking approach to district heating energy. It is one of the first facilities globally to fully merge Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) with biomass combustion in a single operational framework, capable of delivering both electricity and heat, all while recycling waste heat for maximum efficiency.

This ambitious project was developed by Brønderslev Forsyning, the local utility company, as part of Denmark's broader move away from fossil fuels. The motivation was the reduction on the reliance on natural gas and keeping heating costs manageable for residents, especially considering the country's gradual withdrawal from subsidizing gas-fired CHP systems. The investment outcome is a sustainable energy system that now supplies around 90% of Brønderslev's annual district heating demand.

Figure 1 Aerial view of the solar collector field, biomass plant, and outdoor biomass storage area belonging to the Brønderslev hybrid plant. Image source: the Danish

All technical descriptions, data, and figures presented in this section 2 are extracted from the work by Jensen et al. [1], “*Demonstration of a concentrated solar power and biomass plant for combined heat and power*”, which provides a detailed technical description of the design and operation of the Brønderslev CSP-biomass hybrid plant. The same study has been used for operational strategies identification and assessment.

From the point of view of the Use Case I, it is important to note that, within the scope of this use case, the biomass boilers and the ORC unit are not considered part of the integration. The analysis is focused exclusively on the solar thermal field and aims to identify periods throughout the year when the thermal energy produced by the solar collectors is not fully utilized. This non utilized heat represents the primary integration opportunity, serving as the basis for exploring innovative pathways to improve energy valorization and overall system performance with RESTORE concept seasonal storage (see Chapter 3.1 User Case

definition). For this reason, this plant description is focused on those elements that are related to the User Case integration itself and possibly those ones need for a better understanding of the refined data assumptions to be obtained from the plant raw data.

General information about the Use-Case I and its plant, is also described in the public documentation of “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling” concerning WP5 Task T5.4 implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, using the Simulation Web Platform”, available in the project’s Zenodo Community account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>).

2.1. CHP Central Plant background

Before the deployment of the hybrid CSP-biomass system in Brønderslev, the local district heating supply relied on a centralized natural gas based combined heat and power (CHP) facility. This conventional CHP plant has historically played a critical role in providing both electricity and thermal energy to the town’s 4,800 customers, connected via a 160 km-long district heating network. The plant includes seven gas engines with a combined electrical output of 22.8 MW_{el} and thermal output of 30 MW_{th}. Two auxiliary natural gas boilers complement these engines. Each of them with a thermal capacity of 15 MW_{th}, and an electric boiler with a 20 MW_{th} capacity, capable of absorbs surplus electricity from the grid.

In addition to the generation units, the central facility is equipped with a low temperature thermal energy storage system: an 8,000 m³ hot water accumulation tank that can store approximately 450 MWh_{th}. This storage volume allows the plant to balance short-term mismatches between heat production and demand, enabling better utilization of intermittent and price-sensitive energy sources. The tank plays a vital role in buffering peak demands and facilitates load shifting by charging during periods of low demand or high generation (e.g., solar peak hours) and discharging during high consumption periods or when generation is temporarily insufficient.

Figure 2 Schematic of the interconnection of the biomass plant, solar field, and the existing central plant. The forward side (hot) of the district heating loop is shown in blue.

From an operational perspective, the central CHP plant was primarily designed to run continuously at high load factors to capitalize on subsidies and favorable electricity prices in Denmark's energy markets. However, with the expiration of national subsidy schemes for natural gas-fired CHP plants in 2019, the economics of the plant shifted unfavorably. Anticipating this change, Brønderslev Forsyning initiated the hybridization strategy to maintain affordable district heating without increasing customer prices. The integration of the hybrid plant significantly reduces natural gas consumption and offers resilience against fuel price volatility.

The central plant is now used primarily for backup and strategic operation. The high degree of technological flexibility (ranging from internal combustion engines to electric boilers) allows the system operator to dispatch the most economically advantageous unit in response to fluctuating electricity market conditions. For instance, the electric boiler is often activated during hours when electricity prices are low or even negative, particularly during periods of surplus wind generation in Denmark. In contrast, the gas engines are operated during peak price periods to maximize revenue through electricity sales. This responsive dispatch strategy is only possible thanks to the flexibility provided by the storage tank and the coordinated operation with the hybrid plant.

Figure 2 illustrates the hydraulic and thermal interconnection between the central plant, the CSP-biomass hybrid facility, and the district heating grid. All major components are integrated through a common supply and return loop, allowing heat sources to operate in parallel or be decoupled based on operational requirements. This integration is key to achieving both high overall system efficiency and reliability.

In summary, the central CHP plant in Brønderslev may no longer serve as the backbone of energy production, but it still plays a crucial, strategic role within the town's district heating system. Thanks to its established infrastructure and integration with newer hybrid technologies, Brønderslev enjoys a resilient, low-emission, and economically efficient energy supply. In many ways, the town stands as a model for how municipalities can navigate the evolving landscape of sustainable energy.

2.1.1. District Heating Network

The district heating network offers a streamlined and centralized way to distribute heat across residential areas, commercial hubs, and industrial zones alike. With over 160 kilometers of underground piping, the system currently supplies heat to around 4,800 customers (most of them private households). It is built on a closed-loop design, continually cycling water between production facilities and end users while maintaining high thermal stability and minimizing energy loss throughout the seasons.

The network typically operates with a forward temperature near 74 °C and a return temperature close to 35 °C, creating an effective temperature differential of about 40 °C. This thermal setup supports efficient energy delivery while also keeping pumping efforts and heat dissipation within reasonable bounds. As expected, heating demand fluctuates with the weather: cold winters push the system to its limits, while summers see consumption drop dramatically. This

ebb and flow of demand necessitates a dynamic and adaptable energy production portfolio (one that can respond quickly and reliably to shifting consumption patterns).

In recent years, Brønderslev's heating system has averaged an annual heat output of 122 GWh. Still, about 23% of this energy does not reach end users, lost instead of transmission inefficiencies. These losses are attributed to aging insulation, heat seepage into the surrounding soil, and general wear and tear overtime. Even so, such figures remain within the typical range for district heating systems of comparable scale and vintage.

2.2. Hybridized CCP & Biomass Plant

The hybridized plant is composed by a 16.6 MW_{th} parabolic trough collector (PTC) field, two biomass boilers each rated at 10 MW_{th}, and a 3.9 MW_{e1} Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) turbine. These components are linked through a shared thermal oil circuit, using Therminol 66 as the heat transfer fluid. This integrated setup allows the CSP and biomass systems to operate independently or together, feeding heat either to the ORC turbine or directly into the district heating heat exchanger. Such flexibility not only enhances operational resilience but also allows for strategic, real-time optimization based on energy demand and pricing.

Figure 3 Aalborg CSP project engineering design and integration

The combination with the older CHP Plant allows the whole system to adjust to variations in weather conditions or shifts in the energy market. For example, it can focus on producing either electricity or heat, or store energy until it is more profitable to use it.

One of the plant's features is its use of high-temperature solar thermal energy together with biomass to drive a single ORC turbine. This approach differs from earlier CSP-biomass hybrids, which often wasted low-grade heat through cooling towers. In contrast, Brønderslev

redirects that residual heat to the district heating network, significantly boosting overall efficiency. In 2020, the biomass component alone achieved a thermal efficiency of 93.6%, and the ORC unit reached an electrical efficiency of 20.6%.

The system uses commercially available parabolic troughs, conventional biomass boilers, and an off-the-shelf ORC unit. Add to that the shared thermal oil circuit, and you get a model that is both scalable and cost-effective, ready to be adapted in other regions with access to sufficient solar radiation and biomass resources.

2.2.1. CCP Solar field

The solar field comprises forty parabolic trough collectors (AAL-Trough™ 4.0), spread across a 9-hectare site adjacent to the biomass facility. Altogether, they provide an aperture area of 26,930 m², with each mirror spanning 5.77 meters in width. The array is designed to deliver up to 16.6 MW_{th} at peak output. While a true north-south orientation would have yielded slightly better annual performance, the system was aligned 29.9° east of north, a compromise shaped by the irregular layout of the plot and land constraints.

Each collector is composed of four modules, organized into ten parallel loops with each loop extending 125 m in length. These modules concentrate direct solar radiation onto stainless steel absorber tubes encased in vacuum-sealed glass sleeves, a design intended to reduce heat losses through convection and conduction. Heat transfer is carried out by Therminol® 66, a synthetic thermal oil capable of withstanding temperatures up to 340 °C while operating under relatively low pressure.

Parameter	Value
Annual DNI	1 040 kWh/m ²
Total aperture area	26 930 m ²
Row spacing	15 m
Field orientation	29.9° east of north
Cost of CSP field	11.6 million EUR
Maximum collector temperature	340 °C
Mirror width	5.77 m
Collector length	125 m

Figure 4 CSP field and collector parameters.

The field is engineered for two operating modes depending on solar availability and heat demand: (1) ORC mode, delivering high-temperature heat (up to 312 °C) to drive an Organic Rankine Cycle turbine; and (2) district heating mode, which runs at lower temperatures (typically up to 190 °C) to reduce thermal losses during direct feed into the municipal heating network. A feed-forward control system governs the flow rate based on real-time irradiance forecasts and target outlet temperatures.

In 2020, the solar field generated 11.3 GWh of thermal energy, covering 9.5% of the town's heating needs. Although this figure fell short of the projected 16 GWh outlined in the feasibility

study, the shortfall is likely due to overestimated solar irradiation and the accumulation of dirt on the mirrors—no cleaning had been performed since its commissioning in 2017. Even so, the system proved to be reliable and required minimal upkeep, reaching a peak daily conversion efficiency of 57.7% under ideal summer conditions.

2.2.2. Biomass boilers and ORC

The biomass subsystem consists of two identical 10 MW_{th} combustion units that serve as the primary dispatchable heat source of the Brønderslev hybrid plant. Fueled by locally sourced wood chips (primarily pine with an average water content of 42% and a higher heating value of 11.83 GJ/Tn), the system uses both energy efficiency and regional resource utilization.

Each unit is built around a moving-grate furnace and includes a fully automated fuel feeding system. Biomass is delivered daily, stored in covered and uncovered facilities, and transported to the boilers using cranes and hydraulic presses. The combustion process is carefully controlled to avoid slagging, with cooling of the grates using district heating water to extract additional thermal energy.

Flue gases exit the furnace at approximately 950 °C and pass through a two-stage heat exchange system—radiation and convection heaters—which transfer heat to the high-temperature thermal oil loop. An economizer further reduces flue gas temperature to 300 °C and preheats air for combustion, increasing boiler efficiency. This heat exchange process continues through three scrubbers, where residual energy is captured and transferred to heat pumps with a combined capacity of 2 MW_{th}, further boosting system output.

Dust is removed from the flue gases via electrostatic filters, and the final exhaust temperature is reduced to 16 °C after passing through all scrubbers and recovery stages. The plant's flue gas treatment setup is designed for high heat extraction and low environmental impact.

Figure 5 Simplified schematic of the hybrid plant. The thermal oil loop is represented by the yellow lines, and the district heating loop is represented by the red (hot).

In 2020, the biomass units supplied most of the district heating, with a total consumption of 23,430 tons of biomass and an estimated combined electricity and heat output of 72,033 MWh. The total annual efficiency of the biomass plant reached 93.6% (based on higher heating value), though this figure could have been higher if all heat pumps had been operational throughout the year. For part-load flexibility, each biomass boiler can operate down to 30% of its rated capacity, and the two units are connected in parallel to enhance redundancy and load balancing.

The high-efficiency Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) system (Turboden 40 CHPRS Split model) has a nominal electrical output of 3.9 MW_{el}. This unit operates on a regenerative Rankine cycle by employing a high-molecular-weight organic fluid: hexamethyldisiloxane. This design selection allows efficient electricity generation from medium-temperature heat sources, while maintaining lower operational pressures and avoiding the need for constant supervision on-site.

Parameter	Value
HT thermal power ($Q_{oil,ht}$)	18.55 MW _{heat}
HT inlet/outlet temperature	238/312 °C
LT thermal power ($Q_{oil,lt}$)	1.85 MW _{heat}
LT inlet/outlet temperature	135/238 °C
ORC condenser inlet/outlet temperature	40/69 °C
ORC condenser thermal power ($Q_{dh,orc}$)	16.06 MW _{heat}
Nominal electric power output ($E_{orc,net}$)	3.93 MW _{el}
Nominal electrical efficiency ($\eta_{orc,el}$)	19.3 %
Total ORC efficiency ($\eta_{orc,total}$)	98 %

Figure 6 Nominal operating conditions and performance of the ORC unit.

The ORC system is thermally interlinked with two circuits: the high-temperature (HT) and low-temperature (LT) thermal oil loops. The HT loop is primarily heated by biomass boilers, while the LT circuit receives energy from an economizer and, under favorable conditions, from a solar collector field. Respectively, these loops function with inlet/outlet temperatures of 312/238 °C and 238/135 °C. This tiered configuration enables a cascading recovery of thermal energy (each loop feeding the next) which significantly boosts the plant's overall energy efficiency. For this reason, the User case has been based on non-produced thermal energy and available only from the PTC field.

The electricity generation process within the ORC follows the sequence: the organic working fluid is first pressurized by a feed pump, preheated in a regenerator, and subsequently vaporized using the heat exchangers connected to the thermal oil loops. It then expands through a turbine connected to a generator, producing electricity, before finally being condensed by the district heating water. Notably, this method of condensation imposes a thermal ceiling due to the temperature of the district heating network. While it may slightly constrain electrical efficiency, it ensures that all residual heat is recuperated for domestic heating purposes.

The system is optimized for continuous operation, due to the consistent thermal input from the biomass subsystem. When the ORC is offline, the plant is still capable of transferring heat directly from the thermal oil loops to the district heating infrastructure, thereby maintaining uninterrupted service.

In 2020, performance data confirmed that the ORC reached a peak electrical efficiency of 20.6%, closely matching its design expectations.

3. RESTORE TCES Integration

This chapter defines and develops the User Case I, virtually integrating the RESTORE solution into the Brønderslev CHP hybrid plant, described in Chapter 2.

The Brønderslev plant operates with two main renewable heat sources: a parabolic trough collector (PTC) solar field and a set of biomass boilers. The PTC field uses a thermal oil (VP66) as the heat transfer medium and can generate medium-to-high temperature heat (typically between 150–270°C). The oil circulates through various heat exchangers and can either directly feed the district heating (DH) network via a CSP HEX DH or supply an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) module when the temperature reaches adequate levels. In parallel, the biomass boilers provide heat to the same ORC and DH systems, including high- and low-temperature heat exchangers and waste heat recovery lines connected to scrubbers and heat pumps.

This TCES integration has been exclusively integrated into the solar thermal input, since the biomass heat is fully utilized by existing infrastructure. The thermal energy available and captured from the CSP field during the standard operation of the existing facilities (too low DNI, low DNI hours availability during specific days, etc.) is directed fed to the TCES unit for chemical storage.

Figure 7 RESTORE Concept integration in Brønderslev plant

3.1. Use Case definition

TCM Material and Reaction process

A continuously stirred tank reactor for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suspended in thermal oil has been proposed to enhance material reactivity and system integration in TCES RESTORE concept [Wedl et al., 2024]. Copper sulfate pentahydrate has been studied as a thermochemical material suitable for medium-temperature energy storage systems. Its potential lies in its ability

to undergo reversible hydration and dehydration reactions, allowing it to store and release heat through phase transformations. When heated, the pentahydrate first converts into the trihydrate form according to the reaction:

This process continues as the trihydrate transforms into the monohydrate, releasing two more water molecules:

At higher temperatures, the monohydrate dehydrates further into anhydrous copper sulfate:

These successive steps occur over a range of temperatures, enabling gradual and controllable energy storage when paired with solar thermal or industrial heat sources.

The dehydration steps are generally efficient and relatively fast under proper thermal conditions, but the hydration reactions present operational challenges. The rehydration process, particularly the transformation from anhydrous CuSO_4 back to the pentahydrate, can be slow at ambient temperature and low water vapor pressure. This impacts on the system's responsiveness, especially for short-term storage cycles. While earlier studies suggested that the monohydrate might hydrate directly into the pentahydrate, recent evidence indicates that hydration proceeds in reverse order, forming first the trihydrate and then the pentahydrate. This stepwise mechanism reinforces the need to maintain favorable environmental conditions, such as adequate humidity and moderate cooling rates, to ensure complete and timely hydration.

Cycling stability is another key aspect in evaluating $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a thermochemical material. Repeated hydration and dehydration can lead to structural changes in the material, including the formation of cracks and sealed outer layers that block internal water diffusion. These effects reduce hydration completeness over time and lower the material's storage efficiency. To address these issues, innovative approaches are being explored, such as combining the salt hydrate with thermal oil and using direct contact with liquid water instead of moist air. This strategy aims to accelerate hydration, improve thermal conductivity, and enhance the long-term durability of copper sulfate, making it a more viable candidate for integration into thermochemical storage systems used in district heating or renewable-driven energy infrastructures. In RESTORE mineral oil Q-32 has been selected.

Charging process

The TCM charging process within the Brønderslev TCES system begins with the capture of solar energy through a parabolic trough collector (PTC) field non utilized by the existing facilities, which uses a synthetic heat transfer fluid (VP66 oil) to absorb and transport thermal energy. PTC field operates efficiently during periods of high direct normal irradiance (DNI), but primarily in summer months, district heating demand decreases and can be covered partially with this energy, thus a surplus solar energy is not being used. PTC produces in these periods medium-to-high temperature thermal oil (ranging between 150°C and 270°C) suitable for direct integration into downstream thermal applications.

The hot thermal oil that circulates through a closed-loop solar field circuit, pumped by high-temperature pumps and regulated by control valves and sensors that maintain stable operating conditions. Using RESTORE concept, once the fluid reaches the target temperature, it is routed to a primary heat exchanger, where the heat is transferred to the thermochemical loop of the TCES system.

Inside the charging reactor, the TCM undergoes a controlled endothermic reaction, in which heat is absorbed to break molecular bonds and store energy chemically. This transformation occurs under carefully monitored conditions of temperature and pressure, sustained by an external heat exchange interface with the solar oil circuit. The reactor includes internal baffles or packed-bed configurations to enhance heat and mass transfer and ensure uniform reaction progress throughout the material bed.

Prior to entering the reactor, the discharged TCM is preconditioned (heated) to ensure it meets the necessary input specifications. Once the reaction is complete, the material now in its charged chemical form is transported through a sealed piping system to a set of charged-material storage silos or vessels, designed to preserve its thermal and chemical integrity over extended periods.

Figure 8 Case definition concept summary

Discharging process

The discharging phase is activated when there is demand for thermal or electrical energy that cannot be immediately met by direct solar input. In this mode, the charged TCM is extracted from its storage units and directed to a discharging reactor, where it is exposed to conditions that trigger the reverse (exothermic) reaction. This reaction releases the previously stored energy as heat, which is then transferred to the process fluids in the energy conversion system.

The heat released by the exothermic reaction is extracted using a secondary heat transfer loop, often involving a thermal oil or pressurized water circuit that interfaces with an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) system. The ORC module consists of an evaporator, where the working fluid absorbs heat and vaporizes; a turbine, where the vapor expands and generates electricity; a condenser, which returns the vapor to liquid phase; and a recuperator, which recovers residual heat to increase cycle efficiency. The system is complemented by feed pumps, control valves, and thermal insulation systems to optimize energy use and prevent losses.

Simultaneously, part of the heat recovered from the TCM reactor may be directed to a dedicated district heating (DH) heat exchanger, where it is transferred to a water loop that supplies space heating and domestic hot water to residential and industrial consumers. This dual-output configuration allows the TCES system to contribute both to electricity generation and to the heat load of the DHC network, maximizing energy valorization.

Once the TCM has completed the discharging reaction and returned to its lower-energy (discharged) state, it is pumped back to its original storage tanks through a dedicated return loop.

The TCES discharging configuration operates independently of heat pumps or any auxiliary heat recovery systems from the biomass plant, ensuring that the solar storage loop remains a standalone and dispatchable energy module within the hybrid configuration.

3.2. IPSE GO Platform

The RESTORE Virtual Tool is powered by the IPSE GO Platform [3], which is a web-based simulation and optimization environment designed to support the virtual implementation of complex energy systems. Within the RESTORE project, it plays a significant role in the digital representation and testing of six real-world use-cases, each reflecting distinct district heating and cooling (DHC) configurations. The platform allows users to model, simulate, and optimize integrated energy systems combining components such as thermochemical storage, renewable heat sources, and thermodynamic cycles.

One of the core strengths of IPSE GO lies in its flexibility and modular design. It supports the integration of a wide variety of components and subsystems, enabling partners to replicate specific operational settings and boundary conditions from each use-case. For each virtual scenario, the platform facilitates the configuration of heat sources, sinks, storage units, and control strategies, ensuring that the simulation mirrors the physical dynamics of the real installation as accurately as possible.

In addition to basic system modelling, IPSE GO incorporates advanced optimization tools that help evaluate the system's performance under different operational parameters. Users can simulate dynamic behavior over time, analyze energy flows, and test alternative layouts or control algorithms. This supports the identification of the most effective technical solutions for each local context and ensures that the RESTORE concept is not only functional but also efficient and scalable.

The platform also plays a key role in promoting replicability and transparency across the project. Its cloud-based nature facilitates collaboration between project partners, enabling remote access, version tracking, and shared testing environments. By consolidating all use-cases in a unified digital workspace, IPSE GO enables systematic benchmarking, comparison, and validation of the RESTORE solution across diverse European settings.

3.3. Input Data

Data and parameters measured from the plant operation were sent to ACSP team for implementing RESTORE Use-Case I. This information contained data from February 2022 to January 2024. The Use Case has been developed considering as reference the 2023 annual plant operation year and the possible thermal energy from PTC not utilized when DNI conditions allow to produce it and being stored in a TCES.

3.3.1. Initial Raw Input Data

In Figure 9 can be seen the parameters received as raw data for this study, identified by numbers for each stream.

A package of .csv files were compiled from the plant historic system:

Figure 9 2022-24 CSV files

3.3.2. Assumptions

Below, we list the main assumptions that have driven this study for the quantification of the total amount of thermal energy generated by the CSP parabolic trough collectors (PTC) that are not utilized by the main combined heat and power (CHP) plant operation. This allows quantifying the available residual solar thermal energy for storage or alternative uses.

Key assumptions

- 1) Refined data aims to obtain RES Available in the plant, transforming this annual energy into an average hourly Therminol VP-66 flow and temperature
- 2) Expected equivalent hours of operation are based on the numbers of hours the possible thermal energy from PTC not utilized when DNI conditions allowed to produce it and being stored in a TCES.

Input Data Refinement Assumptions

- Hourly timestamps are constructed and aligned with standard calendar hours for 2023.
- Raw solar irradiance data (DNI) is interpolated or averaged hourly, being measured in for Brønderslev.

Solar Resource and CSP Output Assumptions

- CSP energy output is derived based on hourly DNI and an assumed optical efficiency of the collectors.
- A fixed or empirically calibrated optical efficiency is applied uniformly across all hours.
- No thermal inertia is considered in PTC response; output depends only on current hourly conditions.

Thermal Loss Calculation Assumptions

- Convective losses are estimated:
 - With vacuum glass, assuming a 15% residual loss (i.e., 85% reduction in convection losses).
- Radiative losses are computed using a standard Stefan–Boltzmann law:
 - Pipe surface temperature is either assumed constant or modeled hourly.
 - Emissivity and ambient temperature are assumed fixed or simplified.
- Total thermal losses are calculated by summing radiation and convection components, neglecting other minor loss mechanisms.

Power Availability and RES Energy Utilization

- "MAX Power Available" represents the theoretical thermal power output after optical and thermal losses.
- A constant conversion efficiency from solar energy to thermal energy is assumed for this calculation.
- Operational constraints (e.g., system thresholds, dispatch conditions) are not explicitly modeled.

Performance Metrics & Indicators

- Equivalent Operating Hours and Real Fraction of Maximum Power are based on:
 - Normalized output against reference thermal capacity.
 - Assumed full-load capacity remains constant throughout the year.
- No degradation or seasonal derating of system components is considered in these indicators.

3.3.3. Refined Data

A refining process was performed in order to transform the raw data (1, 2, 5 minute basis depending on the parameter) into an hourly basis average to perform the quantification of non-utilized thermal energy in the PTC field, as presented in the table that follows.

Refined Variables Summary			
Variable	Raw Tag / Signal	Original Frequency	Purpose
DNI (Direct Normal Irradiance)	CFA771.CJ401	Every 2 minutes	Estimate hourly solar input for PTC energy generation
Energy Output – Heat Exchanger CSP	CSP.NDA600.CJ401	Every 2–5 minutes	Thermal power from CSP delivered to the system
Outlet Flow from CCP Solar Field	CSP.HUS720.CF491	Every 2–5 minutes	Measure HTF mass flow exiting the collector field
Outlet Temperature from CCP Solar Field	CSP.HSU720.CT401	Every 2–5 minutes	Indicates fluid temperature after solar energy gain
Inlet Flow to ORC	CSP.HUS720.CF493	Every 2–5 minutes	Shows thermal energy available for electricity conversion
Inlet Temperature to CCP Solar Field	CSP.HSU705.CT401	Every 2–5 minutes	Indicates starting temperature of HTF before heating
Inlet Temperature to ORC	CSP.HSU730.CT401	Every 2–5 minutes	Critical for ORC performance and conversion efficiency
Heat Demand from City Network	SA2.BRSLV heat demand	Every 10 minutes	Represents hourly thermal energy demand for DH network

The following Figure 10 quantifies the renewable thermal energy available from the Parabolic Trough Collector (PTC) solar field at the Brønderslev hybrid plant over the course of 2023.

Based on hourly irradiance and plant performance data, the total Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) captured by the 26,930 m² aperture area of the PTC field corresponds to 23.15 GWh across the year. After applying optical and thermal losses, the maximum usable thermal energy from the PTC system is reduced to 16.42 GWh.

From this amount, only 10.11 GWh were effectively used by the existing plant infrastructure (either in the ORC or directly into DH), leaving 5.46 GWh of RES thermal energy unutilized throughout the year.

The monthly breakdown shows that May, June, and April present the highest RES availability, coinciding with periods of high solar irradiance and lower district heating demand. In these peak months, more than 1 GWh per month of usable but unused energy is observed.

A total of 987 hours were identified where solar energy was available but not used, confirming a seasonal mismatch between solar supply and heat demand in the plant. These hours define the operational window during which the RESTORE TCES system can be charged with surplus renewable energy.

Wasted Renewable Energy Source (RES) identification in Brønderslev Hybrid Plant Monthly Accumulated Energy (GWh) – 2023							
PARAMETER / MONTH	DNI Available PTC field Total aperture area 26.930 m2	MAX USABLE ENERGY from PTC (Optical efficiency and Thermal Losses applied)	Brønderslev PTC Output UTILIZED	RES AVAILABLE (MAX - PTC output)	Heat Production from PTC to DISTRICT HEATING	Thermo Chemical Energy Storage (TCES) Power Average sizing	RES AVAILABILITY Equivalent Operations hours
Units	GWh	GWh	GWh	GWh	GWh	MW	HOURS
January	0.318	0.238	0.031	0.121	0.024	8.658	14
February	0.948	0.716	0.242	0.396	0.191	7.192	55
March	1.396	1.050	0.447	0.477	0.358	7.009	68
April	3.474	2.583	1.798	0.705	1.452	4.963	142
May	5.081	3.663	2.278	1.271	1.246	5.749	221
June	4.833	3.388	1.706	1.563	0.857	6.824	229
July	2.747	1.861	1.691	0.132	1.357	1.734	76
August	1.375	0.912	0.738	0.151	0.607	3.092	49
September	1.737	1.151	0.776	0.332	0.602	4.094	81
October	0.831	0.563	0.281	0.213	0.235	5.458	39
November	0.280	0.198	0.077	0.076	0.021	7.573	10
December	0.132	0.097	0.040	0.021	0.004	6.960	3
TOTAL	23.15	16.42	10.11	5.46	6.95	5.78	987

Figure 10 Non-utilized Renewable Energy Source (RES) identification in Brønderslev Hybrid Plant

Following, Figure 11 presents the monthly average and maximum operating conditions of the parabolic trough collector (PTC) solar field in Brønderslev throughout the year 2023. The indicators are based on operational hours in which the solar field was active and is producing heat.

For each month, both the average value during operation and the maximum average value achieved within operational hours were calculated. These values provide insight into the typical and peak thermal energy levels that the system could deliver to downstream processes or thermal storage.

The system maintained a stable and high flow rate from April to September, with values consistently above 72 kg/s. Flow values during winter months (November–January) dropped below 70 kg/s, reflecting reduced solar input and lower system utilization, as can be seen in the figure below.

MONTH / PARAMETER	14	14	16	16
	Outlet temperature FROM CCP SF Operation Hours Average	Outlet temperature FROM CCP SF Operation Hours MAX Average	Outlet Flow FROM CCP SF Operation Hours Average	Outlet Flow FROM CCP SF Operation Hours MAX Average
Units	°C	°C	Kg/s	Kg/s
January	127.4	138.6	67.7	67.7
February	143.4	171.5	70.0	71.5
March	143.8	201.7	72.1	73.2
April	152.0	202.1	76.7	78.3
May	196.1	238.8	78.5	79.9
June	205.7	241.7	77.4	79.6
July	150.7	193.4	74.0	76.3
August	138.8	193.0	70.8	73.1
September	162.6	225.1	72.0	73.1
October	129.8	166.3	70.7	72.0
November	116.2	136.3	68.7	70.9
December	91.8	91.8	66.1	69.1
TOTAL	146.53	183.36	72.06	73.74

Figure 11 User Case HTF fluid (VP-66) average and peaks average flows and temperatures

Regarding the outlet temperature of the solar field, the highest values occurred in May and June, reaching over 238 °C, suitable for ORC or TCES charging. Lowest values appeared in December, with outlet temperatures dropping below 100 °C, insufficient for high-efficiency storage or conversion.

The values selected for this study have been average operating temperature over the year: 146.5 °C and average flow rate during operation: 72.1 kg/s

3.3.4. End-User Feedback

The collaboration with the end user Brønderslev Forsyning has been exemplary throughout the implementation and validation of the RESTORE Use-Case I (UC1) demonstration. The company has shown continuous interest and engagement in the integration of the project.

The ACSP technical team visited Brønderslev plant in February 2025 to capture a detailed understanding of the operation strategy, including how solar thermal, biomass, and ORC technologies are integrated. The site visit allowed the ACSP team to identify integration points and constraints directly with the operational staff.

Following the on-site meeting, Søren Da Costa Mørch (Operations Coordinator at Brønderslev Forsyning) provided additional clarification via email. In particular, he explained the strategy of reducing the PTC thermal oil flow around 13:00 during summer days, despite high DNI levels. This is linked to the fact that: *“The plant usually peaks around 11–12 due to the sun angle. After that, the solar power goes down. We try not to defocus because the CSP plant is our cheapest MW production.”*

Figure 12 Site visit

The support received from the team at Brønderslev Forsyning contributed to the robustness of the simulation of the Use-Case I and the relevance of the techno-economic validation of the TCES system.

3.4. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation.

This chapter defines the implementation performed in the IPSE GO platform for the User Case I simulation, defined for an annual period of time.

3.4.1. UC1 Model definition

The implementation of the thermochemical energy storage (TCES) model in the Brønderslev use-case into the IPSE GO platform has been made using the design and operational strategy proposed by Wedl et al. (2024) in their study titled "Continuously stirred tank reactor for oil-suspended thermochemical energy storage systems for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ", published by the Institute of Chemical, Environmental and Bioscience Engineering at TU Wien.

Main equipment and subsystems of the system that allow the operation for this TCM are (see reference figure from the publication below). The thermochemical storage system based on a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires several dedicated subsystems to perform the charging and discharging reactions effectively.

The main components, based on the experimental setup developed at TU Wien, are:

- (1) Salt Feed Tank: Stores the solid thermochemical material (e.g., $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or its dehydrated forms)
- (2) Mixer Unit: Combines solid salt with recirculated or fresh heat transfer oil (Q32 N) to create a suspension prior to entering the reactor.
- (3) Oil Storage Tank: Supplies fresh oil used in the suspension mixture and thermal circulation.
- (4) Reactor Vessel: The main reaction zone where heat is supplied via an internal heat exchanger to drive the (de)hydration reactions. It includes:
 - Anchor and propeller stirrers for homogenous suspension mixing.
 - Optional nitrogen sparging system to reduce foaming during dehydration.
- (5 & 6) Heat Exchanger System: Provides or extracts heat during charging/discharging via thermal oil, ensuring the reactor maintains the desired operating temperature.
- (7) Condensation Unit and Water Tank: Captures water vapor released during dehydration.
- (8–10) Solid–Liquid Separation Unit: Uses suction filtration or sedimentation to separate reacted salt from oil. Includes:
 - Separator (filter mesh or settling tank)
 - Screw conveyor or rotary valve for salt removal
 - Recirculation loop for recovered oil
- (11) Salt Storage Tank: Receives the reacted (charged or discharged) salt for storage.
- (12) Control and Measurement Cabinet: Contains all electrical and control interfaces, including:

- Oil flow meters, temperature sensors, and water dosing system.
- Speed and direction control for conveyors and pumps.
- Data acquisition system for thermal and chemical process monitoring.
- (13) Water Injection Pump (discharging only): Precisely injects stoichiometric water into the reactor for salt rehydration via a hollow stirrer shaft.

This approach is modular and scalable for pilot and pre-commercial applications like RESTORE's integration at Brønderslev.

Fig. 2. Principle of charging reaction in a continuous stirred tank reactor.

Fig. 3. Principle of discharging reaction.

Figure 13 Charging and Discharging concept: equipment and subsystems

3.4.2. The Charging Mode

The Figure 14 below represents the complete configuration of the TCES system operating in charging mode, as implemented in the IPSE GO simulation platform for Use-Case I (Brønderslev). The process represents the endothermic dehydration of the thermochemical material ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), where thermal energy from the solar field (PTC) is used to charge the TCM by extracting chemically the water.

On the left, the system receives a suspension of discharged TCM from storage, heats it using thermal oil (VP 66 as well has been implements but can be another one in the range of working temperature) and converts it into its dehydrated form. The energy transfer is carried out through a heat exchanger and a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR). After the reaction, the charged suspension is sent to a dedicated storage unit, previously being cooled down using the thermal oil close loop (auxiliary).

Figure 14 Use-Case I - IPSE GO Charging Mode Process

Main systems and equipment functionalities and input values are:

- TC Solar Field (Therminol VP66): it is a renewable heat source for the charging process and provides thermal oil at 146°C and 72.1 kg/s (see chapter 3.3). Outlet from the TCM reactor stream down to 135°C. VP 66 is pumped by the existing facilities pumps group.
- Auxiliary thermal oil loop: TCM Pre-heating / Post cooling Heat Exchangers that Transfers/Remove heat to the TCM suspension loop, increasing temperature efficiently before chemical dehydration begins and decreasing TCM temperature to be stored. Closed loop equipped with a thermal oil pump.
- TCM Reactor (Stirred Tank): where the endothermic dehydration of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ occurs, operating at 125°C. Equipped with internal stirrers and jacketed heat exchange.
- TCM Charging/Discharging Pump System: Regulates the TCM slurry flow from/to TCM storage. Controls feed and recirculation for optimal residence time.
- TCM Separator: partial separation of Q32 N thermal oil of the copper sulphate before being stored.

- Steam condenser: condensate released steam from the TCM reactor.

3.4.3. The Discharging Mode

In the same way, Figure 15 below represents the configuration of the TCES system operating in discharging mode, as implemented in the IPSE Go simulation platform for Use-Case I (Brønderslev). The process models the exothermic hydration of the TCM which releases stored thermal energy upon reaction with water (steam). This heat is subsequently transferred to two outputs: and an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) module for electricity production and district heating (DH) network production

The system receives the charged TCM slurry from the storage tanks. The material is then pumped into the continuously stirred tank reactor (TCR), where steam is injected under controlled conditions to trigger the hydration reaction. The heat released to the ORC cycle. After the reaction, the discharged TCM is directed to its corresponding storage vessel for future reuse.

Figure 15 IPSE Go Discharge process

Below, we describe the main systems and equipment functionalities, as well as the input values of Use-Case I.

- TCM Reactor (Stirred Tank): The reactor operates at 100°C for discharge process. Steam is injected into the reactor to rehydrate the TCM, releasing thermal energy stored during the charging phase.
- Water Pump / evaporator: feed stoichiometric steam directly into the reactor for hydration process.
- Auxiliary thermal oil loop: the same as charging process, adapt TCM temperatures before entering reactor and previously to be stored.
- ORC Module (Organic Rankine Cycle). A second portion of the thermal energy is directed to the ORC evaporator. This subsystem generates electricity by evaporating a working fluid (cyclopentane) using the heat from the reactor loop, expanding it through a turbine, and condensing it with DH water.
- DH Heat Exchanger: transfers a portion of the thermal energy released in the reactor to a pressurized water circuit feeding the Brønderslev DH network. Operating temperatures: 74°C (supply) / 35°C (return).
- TCM Charging/Discharging Pump System / TCM Separator: same as charging process.

4. Results

This section presents the main outcomes of the implementation of the virtual Use-Case I, with the description of the Process Simulations, including: 1. The results of the charging mode scenario; and 2. Respective to the results of the discharging mode scenario. Together, these results provide insights for the technical feasibility of the proposed system.

4.1. Process Simulations

The following subchapters summarize the main process outcomes coming from the IPSE GO model simulations.

4.1.1. Charging Mode

The RES Input Data summary was explained in previous chapters and general outcomes for charging mode are shown in the table below.

- *Renewable Energy Source (RES): PTC Field VP66 Thermal Oil*

Figure 16 Renewable Energy Source

PTC Field VP66 Thermal Oil -Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
PTC Field VP66 Mass Flow	259540	kg/h	Set

PTC Field VP66 Inlet Temperature	146.5	°C	Set
PTC Field VP66 Outlet Temperature	135	°C	
Simulation Results – Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Equivalent operation hours	987	hour	Operation charging hours (Set)
TCM produced	6786	Tn	
Heat consumed	1656146.5	kWh	
Tanks total volume	4145.6	m ³	

The rest of the simulations results are presented in the following tables for each of the main TCES subsystems:

- *TCM Storage and Pumping system*

Figure 17 TCM Storage

TCM Stream Composition FROM Storage– Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
TCM Total Mass Flow	8483	kg/h	
Copper Sulfate	5938	kg/h	70% w/w (Set)

Thermal Oil (Q32N)	2545	kg/h	30% w/w (Set)
Storage Temperature	20	°C	(Set)
Storage Pressure	1	bar	(Set)
TCM impulsion pump	0.75	kW	Power approaches up next motor size
TCM Stream TO Storage– Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
TCM Recirculation	1131	kg/h	18 %
TCM Total Mass Flow	6855	kg/h	
Copper Sulfate	4310	kg/h	63% w/w
Thermal Oil (Q32N)	2545	kg/h	27% w/w
Storage Temperature	35	°C	
Storage Pressure	1	bar	
TCM returning pump	0.75	kW	Power approaches up next motor size

- *Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop for TCM conditioning: Preheating/Cooling and Pumping system*

Figure 18 Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop

Total transferred Heat (Coil)	1677.9	kW	
Preheating Heat	270.4	kW	
Reaction Heat	1407.6	kW	
Reaction Temperature	125	°C	Min-Max Allowed (80-130°C)
Reaction Pressure	1	bar	
TCM Conversion	0.95	Kg/Kg	
Steam Released Mass Flow	1628,1	kg/h	
Steam Released Temperature	125°C		
Steam Released Mass Pressure	1	bar	
Steam Condenser Transferred Heat	1176	kW	
Water Released Temperature	30	°C	Set

4.1.2. Discharging Mode

General outcomes for charging mode are shown in the table below. Discharge hours were set in 700 hours to consider a more extended period of energy/heat production; despite using less capacity of the TCM Reactor (this is due to the different reaction kinetics for hydration/dehydration). Using full TCR capacity the discharge process might be released in about 300 hours.

Simulation Results – Discharging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Duration discharging	700	hour	Operation discharging hours (Set)
TCM consumed	6786	Tn	Same as stored previously (Set)
Electrical energy produced	9627	kWh	
Heat produced	1982709	kWh	

DH Input Data summary was explained in previous chapters:

DH Input Data – Discharging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Inlet Temperature	35	°C	Set
Outlet Temperature	74	°C	Set

The rest of the simulations results are presented in the following tables for each of the main TCES subsystems:

- *TCM Storage and Pumping system*

TCM Stream Composition FROM Storage– Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
TCM Total Mass Flow	9665.8	kg/h	
Copper Sulfate	6077.4	kg/h	63% w/w (Set)
Thermal Oil (Q32N)	3588.4	kg/h	27% w/w (Set)
Storage Temperature	25	°C	(Set)

Storage Pressure	1	bar	(Set)
TCM impulsion pump	1.1	kW	Power approaches up next motor size
TCM Stream TO Storage– Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
TCM Recirculation	2342	kg/h	19.5 %
TCM Total Mass Flow	12007	kg/h	
Copper Sulfate	8419	kg/h	63% w/w
Thermal Oil (Q32N)	3588	kg/h	27% w/w
Storage Temperature	25	°C	
Storage Pressure	1	bar	
TCM returning pump	1.1	kW	Power approaches up next motor size

- *Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop for TCM conditioning: Preheating/Cooling and Pumping system. Water preconditioning.*

Auxiliary Thermal Oil Loop			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Auxiliary Thermal Oil (Therminol VP 66) Total Mass Flow	21835	kg/h	
Auxiliary Thermal Oil (Therminol VP 66) Water preconditioning Mass Flow	5586	kg/h	The auxiliary circuit is utilized also for the Water to Steam conversion (to be fed to the Reactor)
Auxiliary Thermal Oil (Therminol VP 66) TCM preconditioning Mass Flow	16248	kg/h	
Auxiliary Thermal Oil (Therminol VP 66) Pressure	5-6	bar	Pump Suction side – Discharge side
TCM Preheater Heat Transfer	435.3	kW	Preheating TCM from 25°C to TCR Temperature (82.7°C)
Thermal Oil Cooler Heat Transfer	-	KW	Not in operation in Discharge Mode

TCM Cooler Heat Transfer	647.9	kW	Thermal Oil Cooling from TCR outlet 105°C down to 44°C
Auxiliary Thermal Oil Pump	1.1	kW	Power approaches up next motor size

- Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC): Electricity generation and District heating production

Figure 20 ORC Cycle

ORC Discharging – Performance Parameters			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Cycle El. Power Output	14.1	kW	
Net El. Power Output	13.8	kW	
Evaporator Heat from Reactor	298.4	kW	
Condenser Heat Transfer	284.6	kW	
Gross Cycle Efficiency	4.7	%	
Net Cycle Efficiency	4.6	%	
Turbine Pressure Ratio	1.8	-	
Turbine Mass Flow	0.757	kg/s	

Turbine Inlet Volumetric Flow	72.72	l/s	
Turbine Outlet Volumetric Flow	130.00	l/s	
Evaporator U*A	23.00	kW/K	
Condenser U*A	18.34	kW/K	
Recuperator U*A	0.61	kW/K	
DH Mass Flow	6284	kg/h	

- *Thermo-Chemical reactor (TCR) and Steam Released*

TCM Reactor (TCR)– Charging Mode			
Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes
Total transferred Heat (Coil)	298.4	kW	18% of full capacity (driven by Charge Mode capacity)
Preheating Heat	254.9	kW	
Reaction Heat	553.4	kW	
Reaction Temperature	105	°C	Min-Max Allowed (10-130°C)
Reaction Pressure	1	bar	
TCM Conversion	1	Kg/Kg	
Water Feed Mass Flow	2341	kg/h	
Water Feed Temperature	95°C		
Water Feed Mass Pressure	6	bar	
Water Preheater Transferred Heat	190,4	kW	
Raw Water Temperature	25	°C	Set
Water Pump	0.5	kW	Power approaches up next motor size

5. Conclusions

Key conclusions from the implementation of RESTORE Brønderslev Use-Case I are summarized and categorized as follows.

Specific conclusions about integration and feasibility:

- **Seasonal valorization of non-utilized solar thermal energy.** Use-Case I has identified the possible storage of approximately 5.46 GWh/year that is currently not utilized by the facilities and means seasonal mismatches between supply and demand.
- **Strong compatibility between PTC field and TCES requirements.** The average thermal oil temperature (146.5 °C) and mass flow (72.1 kg/s) fall within the optimal range for charging the $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -based TCES reactor, confirming direct integration feasibility.
- **TCES reactor sizing and cycles supported by RES profiles.** Detailed monthly profiles and unutilized energy curves allowed for the definition of reactor capacity, charge/discharge timing, and expected cycle frequency.
- **Full-year dynamic simulation demonstrates operational viability.** The IPSE GO model successfully simulates 987 hours of charging and 700 hours of discharging, confirming that the TCES system can be operated consistently within real plant conditions. Noting that TCM reactions have different energy in play.
- **ORC integration validated with detailed thermodynamic modeling.** Simulated ORC performance shows net efficiency of 4.61%, turbine inlet/outlet flow consistency, and realistic pressure ratios — confirming proper coupling with the TCES discharge cycle.

General conclusions:

- **Brønderslev selected as a candidate for RESTORE concept.** High renewable penetration, presence of a flexible DH network, and non-utilized solar thermal energy make Brønderslev a highly suitable site for RESTORE integration and demonstration.
- **RESTORE approach enhances dispatchability of solar thermal.** The TCES solution enables solar energy to be decoupled from real-time demand, increasing system flexibility, improving renewable integration, and reducing curtailment in hybrid plants.

Next steps and challenges:

- **TCM volumes in play** (thousands of cubic meters) needed for seasonal storage like this User Case (but it seems to be a general point) will condition and impact the economic feasibility of TCES due to the cost of TCM storage tanks and cost of the TC Material itself.
- **Despite $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is confirmed as a viable TCM for DH-scaled systems and material shows high conversion efficiency in dehydration, stable cycling, etc.,** the need for stable temperature condition can reduce the ways of using RES and WEH from part of the sources dependent on non-stable temperatures production along the day or the season.

6. References

- [1] Jensen, A. R., Sifnaios, I., Perers, B., Rothmann, J. H., Mørch, S. D., Jensen, P. V., Dragsted, J. and Furbo, S. (2022) 'Demonstration of a concentrated solar power and biomass plant for combined heat and power', *Energy Conversion and Management*, 271, Art. 116207. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.116207>.
- [2] Wedl, G., Schmieder, L., Hein, C. and Winter, F. (2024) 'Continuously stirred tank reactor for oil-suspended thermochemical energy storage systems for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ', *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 255, p. 123977. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.123977>
- [3] SimTech GmbH, "IPSE GO: cloud-based process simulation software for mass and energy balance calculations," IPSE GO platform, 2025. Available: <https://ipsego.app>
- [4] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766; RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling: General Documentation of WP5-Task T5.4 on the Implementation, Optimization, Management & Validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform, ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), S. Bergmann (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH). Published in the [RESTORE Zenodo Community](#), July 2025.
- [5] European Commission, Horizon 2020 Project RESTORE "Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC", <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036766>, Grant Agreement GA Nr.101036766, August 2020th, 2021.
- [6] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D1.1 - Report on Requirements and Specifications of the Overall Concept (V1), ed.: Francisco Cabello (CENER), March 31st, 2023.
- [7] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D1.4 - Specifications of RESTORE Use-Cases and Models, ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH), September 30th, 2023.
- [8] SIMTECH GmbH, "The Process Simulation Environment IPSEpro", <https://www.simtechnology.com/cms/ipsepro/process-simulation-and-heat-balance-software>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [9] SIMTECH GmbH, "IPSE GO: The Future of Simulation", <https://about.ipsego.app/>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [10] SIMTECH GmbH, "IPSEpro & IPSE GO - Powerful Process and Heat Balance Simulation Solutions", <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/ipsepro-ipse-go-powerful-process-heat-balance-simulation/>, © 2023 SimTech GmbH.
- [7] European Commission, RESTORE Horizon 2020 Project GA Nr.101036766. Deliverable D5.10 - RESTORE Replication Strategy (V1), ed.: F. Dargam (SIMTECH), E. Perz (SIMTECH), November 30th, 2023.